

Step 1. Intake Questionnaire

- Age is just a number!
[Enter your age] _____
- Gender
[Select your gender] _____
- What is your nationality?
[Select your nationality] _____
- Approximately how many minutes/hours per day do you listen to music?

- Approximately how many minutes/hours per day do you **attentively** (with focus) listen to music?

- Approximately how many minutes/hours per day do you **use music streaming platforms** (e.g., Spotify, YouTube, Deezer, Apple Music) to listen to music?

- Have you ever released music on a streaming platform?
Yes / No
- I am very familiar with currently popular music and artists.
Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Neither Agree nor Disagree / Agree / Strongly Agree
- I consider my music taste to be a 'niche'.
Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Neither Agree nor Disagree / Agree / Strongly Agree
- I'm intrigued by musical styles I'm not familiar with and want to find out more.
Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Neither Agree nor Disagree / Agree / Strongly Agree
- How much affinity do you have for these genres?
 - Pop
1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5
 - Hip-Hop / R&B
1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5
 - Rock / Alternative
1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5
 - Electronic / Dance
1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5
 - Jazz / Blues
1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5
 - Folk / World Music
1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5
 - Metal / Punk
1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5
 - Classical
1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5

UI screenshots:

About You

Age is just a number!
Enter your age

Gender
Select your gender

Nationality
Select your nationality

Approximately how many hours per day do you listen to music?

Approximately how many hours per day do you use music streaming platforms (e.g., Spotify, YouTube, Deezer, Apple Music) to listen to music?

Approximately how many hours per day do you attentively (with focus) listen to music?

Have you ever released music on a streaming platform?
Select an option

I am very familiar with currently popular music and artists.
 Strongly Disagree Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Agree Strongly Agree

I consider my music taste to be a 'niche'.
 Strongly Disagree Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Agree Strongly Agree

I am intrigued by musical styles I am not familiar with and want to find out more.
 Strongly Disagree Disagree Neither Agree nor Disagree Agree Strongly Agree

Please rate how much affinity you have for these genres:

Pop
★★★★★

Hip-Hop / R&B
★★★★★

Rock / Alternative
★★★★★

Electronic / Dance
★★★★★

Jazz / Blues
★★★★★

Folk / World Music
★★★★★

Metal / Punk
★★★★★

Classical
★★★★★

Submit